

Growth and Characterization of Non linear Lithium Sulphate Doped 8-Hydroxyquinoline Single Crystal

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Abstract

In the recent years, numerous research activities have been in progress on non linear optical crystals owing to their key functions in optical modulation, optical switching, frequency doubling and optical memory. The present work deals with the crystal growth of lithium sulphate doped with 8-hydroxyquinoline by slow evaporation solution growth method. The grown crystals are characterized by structural, optical, spectral, mechanical, dielectric and thermal studies. The lattice parameters and crystal structure of the grown crystals are measured by single crystal X-ray diffraction. The presence of functional groups in the grown compound has been confirmed by FTIR technique. The suitability of the grown materials for optical application was studied by using UV-Visible spectroscopy. The second harmonic generation efficiency of grown crystals were recorded by Kurtz and Perry technique with Nd:YAG laser using KDP as a standard material. The hardness of the grown crystal was measured by using Vicker's microhardness tester. To analyze the electrical properties, dielectric constant, dielectric loss and a.c. conductivity of the grown compound were calculated from the frequency range 50 Hz – 5 MHz at different temperatures. The melting point and decomposition of the grown material were investigated using thermo gravimetric and differential thermal analyses studies.

Keywords: NLO Material, Crystal Growth, FTIR, Thermal Analysis.

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